

Project GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101019427

Deliverable 4.3 - Report describing Services A and B

Executive Summary

Delivering on its mission, PALOMERA has developed a rich Knowledge Base (KB)¹ containing over 650 open access (OA) policy and related documents, a report describing the results of over 450 responses from across the ERA to a large survey performed by the project, and a set of 40 stakeholder interviews. The Knowledge Base forms the basis of the research undertaken in WP3 providing a unique overview of the OA books² policy landscape in Europe. Some of this research has been distilled into short and well communicated articles published through the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit.³ Moreover, actionable recommendations have been developed to eight stakeholder groups based on this research and the Knowledge Base. To support the alignment of OA books policies, two services have been developed/designed as per the Grant Agreement: **1) the Funder Forum** has been established where research funders and policymakers benefit from knowledge exchange and mutual learning, and **2) a Policy Development Tool** has been conceptualised to help funders and institutions navigate the process of policy formulation and implementation. Both services are envisioned to support the project's overall goal of accelerating the transition to open access for books. Whereas the Funder Forum could provide a useful instrument for RFOs and RPOs for knowledge exchange, mutual learning and coordination of services to support the implementation of OA book policies and strategies, the Policy Development Tool holds the potential to specifically help those RFOs and RPOs who want to develop a policy. Furthermore, the Policy

¹ <https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/home>

² In alignment with the Grant Agreement, we define 'books' in this document as scholarly peer reviewed books including monographs, academic book chapters, edited collections, critical editions, and other long-form scholarly works.

³ <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/>

Development Tool would also be closely aligned with the Funder Forum, where the tool could be further developed to better serve the needs of the RFOs in consultation with RPOs.

This deliverable (D4.3) will describe these two services. Both services are intended to support and help coordinate aligned development of policies and strategies for OA books as defined in the Grant Agreement as the outcomes of T4.2 (WP4). In the Grant Agreement the two services are named Service A (the Funder Forum) and Service B (the Policy Development Tool).

The deliverable will describe how the Funder Forum was established and provide a brief summary of each of the four Funder Forum meetings held during the project and their outcomes. Moreover, it will stipulate a sustainability plan for the Funder Forum to ensure its continuation beyond the project's lifetime in alignment with the project's exploitation plan.

The deliverable will also describe the concept design of the Policy Development Tool (Service B). This tool will be described as a potential exploitable outcome of the building of the Knowledge Base (WP2), and based on the research (WP3) and the recommendations (WP4). The idea of the service is to provide RFOs and RPOs with a tool helping them to formulate and implement policies and strategies for OA books.

Keywords :

Open Access books, policy,
funder forum,
policy development tool,

Document identification

Work Package	WP4		
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Type⁴	R-Document, report	Dissemination level⁵	Public (P)
Status⁶	Under EC review	Due date	2024/10/31
Version	D4.3 V1.5 final	Submission date	2024/10/31

Document history

Version⁷	Date	Change editors name	Changes
1.0	2024/07/16	Laura Bandura-Morgan	Drafting part Service A, collecting input
1.1	2024/09/20	Niels Stern	Editing part Service A and drafting part Service B, collecting input
1.2	2024/10/04	Perry Collins, Bregt Saenen	Minor changes and some improvements suggested
1.3	2024/10/21	Niels Stern, Laura Bandura-Morgan	Implemented feedback from reviewers
1.4	2024/10/30	Niels Stern	Updated section 2.2.4 based on the outcome of the 4th FF meeting
1.5	2024/10/31	Niels Stern	Small edits in the document based on input from contributors

Quality control

Role	Name (Beneficiary short name)	Approval date
Project manager (Quality)	Mandy Y. Lin (OPERAS)	2024/10/31

⁴ Retain as applicable.

⁵ Retain as applicable.

⁶ Retain as applicable.

⁷ Use 2.0, 2.1, etc. if the version is updated after the EC rejection.

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	
APC	Article Processing Charge
BPC	Book Processing Charge
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
CRIS	A current research information system
D#	PALOMERA project Deliverable
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ERC	European Research Council
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESF	European Science Foundation
EU	European Union

Acronyms	
FAIR	Findable. Accessible. Interoperable. Reusable.
FF	Funder Forum
FWF	Austrian Science Fund
IBL PAN	Instytut Badań Literackich Polskiej Akademii Nauk
KB	Knowledge Base
KER	Key Exploitable Results
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
M#	Month
NWO	Dutch Research Council
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Book Network
OABT	OAPEN OA Books Toolkit
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OS	Open Science
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (while in this document it will be referred to as Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation Plan)

Acronyms	
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors
RFO	Research Funding Organizations
RPO	Research Performing Organizations
SPARC Europe	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition
SO#	Specific Objective
SE	Science Europe
SNSF	Swiss National Science Foundation
T#	Task
UGOE	Georg August Universität Göttingen
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
WP#	Work Package
ZRC SAZU	The Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

The following PALOMERA partners took part in Task 4.2. activities

WP4 Task 4.2 participants			
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1. Introduction

1.1 Objectives for the work

In the Grant Agreement, the PALOMERA project-specific objective (SO4) was defined to provide resources to support institutional developing the strategies and funder policies for open access to books.⁸ In particular these resources should function as practical services or tools for coordination of policies, sharing of good practices and developing strategies for OA books amongst RFOs and RPOs. As described in the proposal under task 2 of WP4 (T4.2) the activities were focused on two main outcomes, services A and B.

Service A was inspired by a feasibility study of the ERC-OAPEN-2019 project⁹, which explored the interest of increased collaboration and coordination of A book related issues (policy, infrastructure, services etc.) amongst several national funders. Based on that study, the idea was to create a trusted forum for the exchange of knowledge and experiences around OA book policymaking, to be named the Funder Forum. The forum would help ensure the coordination of policies and strategies for OA books.

Service B was planned to be only described and designed as a Policy Development Tool. This tool was planned to be based on the Knowledge Base (WP2), the research undertaken in WP3, and the recommendations coming out of WP4. The idea of this service is to provide RFOs and RPOs with a tool helping them to formulate and implement policies and strategies for OA books.

⁸ In the Grant Agreement, we define (academic) books as scholarly peer reviewed books including monographs, book chapters, edited collections, critical editions, and other long-form scholarly works. In the remainder of this text, we will consistently refer to ‘academic books’ to avoid all ambiguity.

⁹ Grant agreement ID: 964352, <https://doi.org/10.3030/964352>

2. Service A: Funder Forum

2.1 Introduction

2.1.1 Establishing the Funder Forum

The idea of creating a Funder Forum emerged from the public research community when several European research funders (including [FWF](#), [SNSF](#), [NWO](#), [UKRI](#), [DFG](#), [ERC](#) and the [EC](#)) participated in a workshop on OA books in October 2021 organised by OAPEN. A common interest was expressed to have OAPEN coordinate a forum where research funders could convene to discuss OA books. As scientific coordinator of the PALOMERA Project and T4.2 leader, OAPEN therefore embarked on establishing the Funder Forum together with the task participants. From the outset, it was important that the Funder Forum would be inclusive and open to all research funders in the European Research Area (ERA) while also connecting with funders from outside the ERA.

The Funder Forum was established to facilitate the exchange of practices and experiences between research funders about policies designed to promote open access to academic books, and – where possible – align such policies and practices. One important objective of the Forum was to explore ways to deal with challenges and obstacles identified by the participants collaboratively. In addition, Funder Forum members would be invited to participate in the development of the OAPEN infrastructure and its service provision to research funders¹⁰ to embed the project results within existing community initiatives.

The Funder Forum was set to meet twice a year in the two-year lifetime of the PALOMERA project, two online meetings (2-3 hours) in the first year and one online meeting and one in-person meeting in the second year were planned. It was also planned that the Funder Forum members would agree on the continued existence of the Funder Forum before the end of the project. Those funders who should wish to continue to participate would then decide on a governance and funding model for its continuation.

2.1.2 Identification of participants of the Funder Forum

Having decided on these initial elements for establishing the Funder Forum, the next step was to identify the research funding organisations (RFOs) in the European Research

¹⁰ <https://oapen.org/funders/13139405-services-funders>

Area (ERA) countries that represent agencies financing research, along with their representatives responsible for open science activities, including policy development.

As described in the PALOMERA Data Collection Methodology¹¹ there are 39 countries associated with the ERA from which data were collected and analysed. Twenty-nine of the ERA countries have funding organisations that are engaged as members of Science Europe, the association supporting excellence in science and research across all disciplines (see Table 1).

Table 1

European research countries included in the data collection in the PALOMERA project.

Countries where no RFOs have been identified are marked in red.

European Research Area countries			
Science Europe members			non-SE members
Austria	Iceland	Romania	Albania
Belgium	Ireland	Serbia	Bosnia and Herzegovina
Czechia	Italy	Slovakia	Bulgaria
Croatia	Latvia	Slovenia	Cyprus
Denmark	Lithuania	Spain	Greece

¹¹ Maryl, M., Manista, G., Păltineanu, S., Stone, G., Laakso, M., Dreyer, M., Bandura-Morgan, L., Davidson, A., Silva Ferreira, N. H., Snijder, R., Tummes, J.-P., & Varachkina, H. (2024). PALOMERA D2.1 Report on Compiling the Knowledge Base. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10777132>
<https://zenodo.org/records/10777132>

Estonia	Luxembourg	Sweden	Malta
Finland	Netherlands	Switzerland	Moldova
France	Norway	Ukraine	Montenegro
Germany	Poland	United Kingdom	N.Macedonia
Hungary	Portugal		Turkey

Figure 1
Member organisations of Science Europe ([Members - Science Europe](#))

The first step was to contact representatives of RFOs from the members of Science Europe as potential attendees of the Funder Forum. Currently, there are 37 research funding organisations that are member organisations of the Science Europe association (see Figure 1). Additionally, representatives from the other funding institutions from SE-member countries, including public and private foundations, were identified and are listed below in Table 2.

Table 2

Other organisations from SE-member countries from which representatives were invited to FF meetings

Funder name	Country
Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG)	Austria
Kone Foundation	Finland
Royal Irish Academy (RIA)	Ireland
Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information (CVTISR)	Slovakia
Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT)	Spain
Riksbankens Jubileumsfond (RJ)	Sweden
The Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development (ZonMw)	The Netherlands
Wellcome Trust	United Kingdom
The British Academy	United Kingdom

Representatives were also identified from funding organisations from ERA countries who were not SE member countries. These are listed in Table 3.

Table 3*Organisations from non-SE countries from which representatives were invited to FF meetings*

Funder name	Country
Bulgarian National Science Fund (BNSF)	Bulgaria
The Research and Innovation Foundation (RIF)	Cyprus
Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.)	Greece
The Malta Council for Science and Technology (Xjenza)	Malta
National Agency for Research and Development (ANCD)	Moldova

Additionally, we invited individuals from certain countries who were directly involved as experts or reviewers in the development of OA book policies at the national or European level. This includes representatives from organisations listed in Table 4.

Table 4*Organisations from which the expert were invited to be part of FF*

Organisation name	Country
University of Cyprus Library	Cyprus
University of Zagreb	Croatia
National Open Research Forum (NORF)	Ireland
National Research Council (CNR)	Italy
Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM)/UNESCO	Poland
Kungliga biblioteket	Sweden

We were also able to invite representatives from the European Commission, the European Research Council, and US funding organisations, such as the National Science Foundation (NSF), the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), and the Australian National Centre for the Public Awareness of Science.

Unfortunately, as representatives from funders in Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Turkey were not identified, these organisations did not participate in PALOMERA Funder Forum meetings (marked in red in Table 1).

In total, we identified representatives from 56 RFOs in 34 ERA countries and invited them to participate in the Funder Forum meetings. Not all invitations were successful; some organisations did not respond, while others kindly declined the invitation due to a lack of capacity or resources, or because they had no interest in developing an OA book policy at that time.

The map below represents the countries (24) whose representatives attended at least one of the four Funder Forum meetings.

Figure 2

ERA countries whose representatives attended at least one of the four Funder Forum meetings

2.2 Funder Forum meetings

The Funder Forum (FF) meetings were scheduled twice a year during the spring and autumn seasons. The first three meetings were organised as online events, while the fourth was part of the final conference, held in person as a one-day workshop in Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Invitations were sent in advance of each meeting via email, and the agenda for each upcoming meeting was also published on the PALOMERA dedicated page.¹² The same page also encouraged interested RFOs not yet part of the Funder Forum to email the organiser if they wished to take part.

All Funder Forum meetings were held under the Chatham House Rule,¹³ meaning participants were free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, could be revealed.¹⁴

All partners in Task 4.2 were involved in the preparation of the Funder Forum meetings, and some acted as moderators and note-takers. Twelve preparatory meetings took place. In addition to the PALOMERA project partners engaged in Task 4.2 activities, members of the PALOMERA Advisory Board also participated actively in the meetings.

Each meeting is described in some detail below. In summary, the meetings were designed to create a trusted space for the participants (funders and policymakers) where they could feel comfortable sharing their views and experiences and identifying problems and challenges and sharing best practices. To enable this trust-based space, meetings were by invitation only, held under the Chatham House Rule, abiding by the PALOMERA privacy policy. The (anonymised) minutes of the meetings were shared after each meeting for comment before being archived in a dedicated project folder. Based on this meeting framework each event was built on the experience of the previous one(s), in addition to knowledge gathered between meetings (section 2.3).

¹² <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/results/palomera-funder-forum/>

¹³ <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule>

¹⁴ This was explained in the programme as follows: *The meeting will be held under the Chatham House Rule, which means that participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed. The meeting will not be recorded but notes will be taken. No personally identifiable information will be reported and responses to questions, discussion and comments will be summarised only. Should you wish to stop participating, this can be done at any time without any repercussion, however, due to the anonymised nature of any summary report, it may not be possible to identify and remove inputs after the point at which they are anonymised. The summarised and anonymised input of the group discussions will be shared with you and the other participants and used by the PALOMERA project to perform analyses relevant to the project. PALOMERA data privacy policy <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/privacy-policy-palomera>*

The first meeting was very lively with small group discussions on the broad themes of OA book policy development and implementation to get everyone engaged and to note the areas of most interest to the participants. After the first meeting we had a better sense of the topics of most interest to the participants and also an understanding that learning from others' experience was desired. The second and third meetings therefore showcased how different funders have developed and implemented their policies and how some were still in the process of being developed. During these meetings we also managed to test concrete ideas with the participants (e.g. on supporting infrastructures) and we spent time sharing the research findings of the project and project outcomes like the Knowledge Base. We believed it was important that the final meeting would be in-person although we knew that this might potentially reduce the number of participants. Connecting the last Funder Forum meeting to the project conference seemed like the best option and fortunately we managed to have representatives from funding agencies in 10 countries attending this meeting where we discussed important aspects of the forum's continuation and sustainability opportunities, which will be described below.

Overall, through PALOMERA we have managed to gather research funders and policymakers focussing on open access books in a structured and recurring format which is unprecedented to the best of our knowledge. As described in section 2.2.4 and in the Exploitation plan (D5.1)¹⁵ the Funder Forum will be continued beyond the project period, building on the momentum we have created with funders and policy makers.

2.2.1 Funder Forum meeting #1

The 1st Funder Forum meeting was held on 23 May 2023. Duration: 2.5 hrs.

Attendees: Representatives from 23 RFOs in ERA countries participated, along with two representatives from US funding organisations, one from Australia, and three PALOMERA Advisory Board members. In total, 47 attendees were present.

Objective: The main purpose was to understand the state of OA book publishing and policy development in the representatives' countries, considering political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors (PESTLE). In addition, we explored the role of each agency in establishing a policy on OA books.

The focus of this first meeting was on the benefits funders could gain by sharing their experiences, best practices, and challenges in developing or implementing OA book policies. We used breakout rooms with 5–6 participants to foster discussion and create an environment for mutual learning. Questions were prepared in advance to structure the discussion, providing a starting point for engagement and dialogue. This format ensured that everyone had a chance to contribute and listen, stimulating different ways

¹⁵ Rabar, U., Barnes, L., Proudman, V. (2023) <https://zenodo.org/record/7733579#.ZBCI0y8w17M>

of thinking and interaction. It also facilitated more personal and informal conversations among participants.

A few sample questions for the breakout room discussions are listed below:

1. Please describe how academic books are included in national conversations around open science in your country. If they are not, then what do you think are the reasons why they are not included?
2. What is the financial situation in your country, and how is higher education prioritised? How are public funded projects related to open science?
3. What are the researchers' opinions/attitudes in your country towards open access to books? What are the issues they raise?
4. What is the publishing landscape and how do the infrastructures for publishing work, etc.? Are there any underlying infrastructures that might support the policy or are supporting the policy?
5. Are there any legal aspects (burdens) that have to be taken into consideration while developing an open access policy for academic books, like copyright or intellectual property law? Are researchers obliged to any rightsholder organisations?
6. What is the relationship between all partners in the research environment: publishers, librarians and authors in collaboration towards open access to publications, in particular to books?

Insights from each focus group were presented during the plenary session. A short poll was conducted to determine the themes of greatest interest to the participants that fed into the design of the 2nd Funder Forum meeting. Based on 35 responses, the topics of most interest included:

- Business and publishing models for OA books;
- Funding mechanisms towards grantees, including timing beyond the project lifetime;
- Technical infrastructures; and
- Common evaluation framework (research assessment).

The poll was supported by further comments from a group discussion. One of the participants stated: *I would say maybe there should be a forum for funders **to share their best practices**. cOAlition S is not about books, but a forum to discuss this has been very valuable. I wonder if something like that is a first step. Maybe to start there.*

The first Funder Forum meeting was considered successful and fruitful, attracting many RFO representatives, including participants from the United States, and as such it served as a foundation for future meetings. This encouraged us to formulate the recommendations of the first policy brief that was submitted at the end of the first reporting period in M9 (as deliverable D4.1¹⁶) recommending that research funders would agree on a support mechanism for the continuation and future coordination of the Funder Forum.

2.2.2 Funder Forum meeting #2

The 2nd Funder Forum meeting was held on November 20, 2023. Duration: 2.5 hrs.

Attendees: Representatives of 23 RFOs from ERA countries participated, plus funder representatives from the US (NSF and NEH) and PALOMERA project members. In total, there were 39 participants.

Objective: The agenda for this meeting was created based on the topics proposed by the funders during the 1st meeting, as well as the request for knowledge exchange and mutual learning.

Four representatives from the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), the Norwegian Research Council (RCN), UKRI, and the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) were invited to present the current situation in their countries regarding the development and implementation of open access book policies. This was in line with the project's specific objective (SO2), which focused on understanding the challenges preventing RFOs from developing and aligning their policies for OA books. These four funders - although representing countries of very different size, also in terms of research outputs - were chosen because they all have policies in place.

The plenary session that followed the group discussions allowed participants to pool together the major issues raised during the sessions, which are the most troublesome for funders. Some of these issues are listed below:

- existing funding models considering how to finance authors, infrastructure or organisations also beyond the funded project,
- alternative forms of funding, including Diamond OA for books,
- monitoring of policy compliance and the cost of OA books,

¹⁶ Stern, N., Rooryck, J. (2023), <https://zenodo.org/records/8402385>

- measuring authors satisfaction or the visibility of books combined with incentives and other benefits,
- bibliodiversity and small language country publishing,
- quality assessment taking into consideration cultural differences, and
- sustainability of open access monographs/books.

As open infrastructure for books was identified as one of the four topics of greatest interest to funders, Niels Stern from the OAPEN presented information on how OA infrastructure providers can support funders in implementing OA book policies.

This meeting was considered very informative not only for funders but also for the project partners. It inspired the setting up of a short survey for funders, in which they were asked to describe the most important challenges they encountered while developing or implementing open access book policies. The survey questions were again structured based on the PESTLE factors. Response details can be found in section 2.3.1.3.

One of the five questions focused on how the Funder Forum can help overcome these challenges, and what would encourage funders to join future meetings. The majority of funders indicated that sharing open access practices, approaches taken by those who developed policies to overcome challenges, and best practices/case studies would be valuable for learning from one another. A few participants raised the issue of how developing open access book policies looks from an Eastern/Central European perspective and how learned societies could be more involved in a community-based scholarly communication ecosystem. Some funders mentioned that they would be interested in further discussions about the development of OA book publishing, including Diamond OA or alternatives to the BPC model.

These ideas were considered when developing the agenda for the 3rd Funder Forum meeting.

2.2.3 Funder Forum meeting #3

The 3rd Funder Forum meeting which was held on May 14, 2024. Duration: 2 hrs.

Attendees: Representatives of 12 RFOs from ERA countries, plus two representatives from the PALOMERA Advisory Board and PALOMERA project members. In total, there were 29 attendees.

Objective: The main goal of this meeting was to continue to share case studies of the country-specific situation in developing and implementing OA book policies, this time, in Belgium and Slovenia.

During this meeting, representatives from the Fund for Scientific Research in Belgium (F.R.S. - FNRS) and the Slovenian Research Agency (ARIS) presented their approaches to OA policy development, primarily considering the current law. These two countries were chosen to give examples of funders with emerging policies (as opposed to the four presentations at the second FF meeting). For the partners of the PALOMERA project, this meeting was also an opportunity to present the Knowledge Base¹⁷, which contains all policies and other relevant documents collected during the project in a coherent format for a wider group of users.

Some representatives of funders were already familiar with the data collected in the Knowledge Base as they were invited in January 2024 to participate in a validation exercise of the data collection (see details in section 2.4.2). However, it was their first introduction to the Knowledge Base for the majority, and their feedback was very valuable.

The idea behind creating the Knowledge Base was to develop a living collection of documents, such as reports, policies, surveys, and statistics, relevant to OA book-related policies in the ERA. Funders and other users can use this resource for developing or updating existing OA policies for books or to get an overview of the funding landscape. Additionally, the leading partner of WP3 explained the data analysis¹⁸ process that has already been performed with the collected evidence on policy mapping. Funders were also engaged in a Mentimeter poll to provide themes of interest for inclusion in the discussion panel that would be organised during the PALOMERA final conference in Ljubljana in October 2024 (see details in section 2.2.4). Of the six proposed topics, funding models and research assessment of open access books garnered the highest interest, each receiving seven votes from a total of 26 participants (see Figure 3).

¹⁷ <https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/home>

¹⁸ Laakso, M., Bandura-Morgan, L., Bazeliuk, N., Davidson, A., Dreyer, M., Iannace, D.E., Manista, G., Maryl, M., Matthias, L., Ozkan, O., Proudman, V., Păltineanu, S., Silva Ferreira, N. H., Stone, G., Tummes, J.-P., Wnuk, M., & Varachkina, H. (2024) PALOMERA Deliverable 3.1 – Report on Analysis Findings, <https://zenodo.org/records/13827251>

Figure 3

Mentimeter poll results indicating funder preferences for the theme topics for the next Funder Forum

2.2.4 Funder Forum meeting #4

The 4th Funder Forum meeting was held on 29 October 2024 as a half day (4 hrs) in-person workshop during the PALOMERA final conference held at the Scientific Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU) Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Attendees: 12 representatives, representing ten research funding organisations and one member of the PALOMERA Advisory Board. Twelve PALOMERA project partners also attended. One participant, representing one country, that was unable to join sent a written statement before the workshop which was shared among all the participants.

Objectives: The main purpose of this 4th Funder Forum meeting was to discuss the future of the Funder Forum, the Knowledge Base, and the Policy Development Tool.

2.2.4.1 Funder Forum

Participants were given a set of questions to consider ahead of the workshop to discuss the future of the Funder Forum. These questions were based on the PALOMERA exploitation strategy. At the workshop, they were asked to consider the governance, coordination, and funding of the Funder Forum beyond the project. They were divided

into three small groups of eight people. After approx. 1 hour and 15 minutes groups re-convened and presented the outcome of their discussions in plenary.

Group feedback emphasised that Funder Forum meetings had been useful, inspiring, inclusive, and well-managed. There was therefore consensus on the need to continue the Funder Forum building on the momentum that has been created during the project. There was also overall alignment between the groups about a possible direction for the Funder Forum. Some observations from the group discussions included:

- The Funder Forum has the right people attending in an engaged way.
- It would be good to find a safe place for the future Funder Forum, for example, in an existing organisation/framework that is already engaging with research funders (a neutral platform).
- Potential hosts for the Funder Forum, could be Science Europe or cOAlition S or it could be an intersection between Science Europe, cOAlition S, OAPEN and relevant observers (e.g. SPARC Europe, CONOSC and EUA).
- The framework should be as lightweight as possible to avoid the duplication of effort.
- It is important to have a forum dedicated to books because they have special needs (infrastructure, funding, distribution etc.) and support 'slow' science.
- Goals for the Funder Forum could be:
 - Knowledge exchange (focus on practical case studies and funding mechanisms)
 - Policy alignment and development, bring PALOMERA project findings to policy platforms
 - Develop the Policy Development Tool
 - Implement PALOMERA recommendations in the next 2-3 years?
- Expertise that could be provided to the Funder Forum, for example include:
 - cOAlition S (include OA books action in the future?)
 - OAPEN (service provider)
 - OPERAS Special Interest Groups dedicated to OA books (advice and community input and consultation)
 - EUA, SPARC Europe (connector to other stakeholders like RPOs and national policymakers (CONOSC)).
- Meeting frequency should be manageable. However, ensure continued attention, for example quarterly meetings.
- Next meeting should preferably be in February 2025 (to avoid losing the momentum) where further plans could be developed.
- Creating an interim plan to ensure a February meeting would be advisable.
- Financial commitment to sustain the Funder Forum was not proposed (and perhaps not believed as necessary in the first instance), however any financial support should not be based on micro-payments but rather on larger investments.

- One needs to decide on where future FF documentation would be archived safely.

Three action points came out of this first workshop:

1. Science Europe to investigate the potential involvement of their policy platform as a safe future place for the Funder Forum with the involvement of cOAlition S, OAPEN and other relevant organisations like SPARC Europe and EUA.
2. Consider a next Funder Forum meeting in February 2025 (to be organised by OAPEN if Science Europe is still investigating options).
3. To inform the funders (also those who did not attend the 4th Funder Forum meeting) about progress of the above actions.

2.2.4.2 Knowledge Base

The first part of the second workshop of the Funder Forum meeting was dedicated to the Knowledge Base. Scenarios for the continued maintenance of the Knowledge Base were presented in plenum.

Scenario I

- Funder has their own account credentials and direct access to the KB
- Funder can upload new documents at any time
- Contact OAPEN for any support

Scenario II

- Funder is asked by OAPEN twice a year whether there are any new documents in their country that might be uploaded into KB
- Funder will provide OAPEN with documents
- OAPEN uploads the document into KB

Note: requires financial support for administrative resources.

Scenario III

- OAPEN conducts a search for new policy documents in the country and consults with Funder whether this document is relevant
- OAPEN uploads the document into KB

Note: requires financial support for administrative resources or OPERAS National Nodes can serve as potential contributors - subject to availability of a National Node in particular countries.

There were no immediate decisions taken on which scenario would be preferable among the participants. However, it was stated that the Knowledge Base is a very valuable resource for funders and other stakeholders. To ensure its continued value and relevance, a plan for ongoing maintenance and how new material will be added to the Knowledge Base needs to be decided upon.

2.2.4.3 Policy Development Tool

The concept of the policy development tool (Section 3) was presented during the second part of the second workshop as an exploitation of the Knowledge Base and the PALOMERA research, particularly the development of key policy elements (see Figure 4).

Figure 4

Key policy elements derived from the PALOMERA research

Following this presentation, there was a discussion about how such a tool could be developed and connected to the Knowledge Base. For example, by extracting examples of policies (text excerpts) that would serve as helpful examples for those writing policies. A lively and useful discussion ensued and it appeared obvious that the (co-)creation of the Policy Development Tool could be an objective for the Funder Forum (as foreseen in the Grant Agreement).

As a result, both the Knowledge Base and the Policy Development Tool will be discussed in future Funder Forums.

2.3 Other interactions and engagement activities related to the Funder Forum

To gain a broader perspective on the factors that might influence a funder's decision-making process in developing an OA policy – particularly concerning books – various activities and events were organised between the Funder Forum meetings. These initiatives aimed to better understand the role that funders play in the research ecosystem.

Most of these activities were organised by PALOMERA partners responsible for tasks in WP5 related to outreach and engagement (T5.2). This included cross-project collaboration webinars organised by PALOMERA, DIAMAS, and CRAFT-OA, as well as surveys and validation exercises for the data collected during the project and the final recommendations. Additional activities also took place as part of WP4 tasks.

2.3.1 Surveys

2.3.1.1 PESTLE survey

As mentioned in section 2.2.2, following an inspirational Funder Forum meeting in November 2023, a five-question survey was distributed among the funders as a follow-up activity. They were asked about the most important challenges they observe or encounter while developing or implementing OA book policies. Respondents were prompted to rate the challenges on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 was considered of low importance and 5 was considered very important. Invitations were sent to 37 funder representatives and 19 responses were collected (response rate: 51.4%). The results are shown below in Figure 5.

Figure 5

Political (a), economic (b), social (c), technological (d), legal (e), and (f) environmental challenges encountered by funders when developing an OA book policy

ECONOMIC challenges

19 responses

SOCIAL challenges

19 responses

TECHNOLOGICAL challenges

19 responses

LEGAL challenges

19 responses

ENVIRONMENTAL challenges

19 responses

As can be seen from Figure 5, funder responses indicate the importance of the economic factor for developing or implementing open access book policies; 17 out of the 19 respondents agreed that economic factors have an important or very important impact on policy development. This was also reflected in the answers to subsequent questions. Funders were asked to provide examples of these specific challenges. In summary, a few of the most important challenges that funders reported are (verbatim):

- The budget of the agency relies closely on political and economic stabilisation of the government.
- The university/library sector is under economic pressure and additional costs for monographs will increase this unless new publishing models gain traction.
- The sustainability of funding OA business models, also after project ends,
- High BPCs costs.
- Lack of sufficient staff.

Other challenges, which were also mentioned by funders include:

- Social attitudes specifically internally may cause the funding of OA books not to be viewed as a priority.
- Raising awareness about funding availability for open access books.
- Publishing culture in SSH, negative view of OA books and a fear of losing the prestige of printed books.
- Monitoring of compliance with Open Science requirements due to incomplete metadata.
- Lack of rights retention/secondary publishing rights options for books.

When asked how the Funder Forum can help overcome these challenges and what might encourage them to consider joining future meetings, funder representatives mentioned that (verbatim):

The FF helps me to have a clear picture on what others are doing across the globe.

The Funder Forum helps demonstrate the diversity of the ecosystem of OA books and the importance of an aligned strategy on policy implementation (ex-members of Plan S versus outsiders).

Learning about how other funders have implemented policies around OA books has been very useful in providing ideas for potential future directions.

Would be interested to discuss further developments of OA book publishing such as diamond OA/alternatives to BPC models or also still remaining legal questions in the publishing process (image rights) and struggles with the monitoring of OA books and their metadata or possibilities/examples of the funding of alternative publication

formats (beyond book formats). Otherwise, we are also happy to share our experiences concerning the challenges mentioned above.

Furthermore, shed light on European policies that might be the catalyst to change local/government policies/strategies.

Designing a common sustainability model for OA books.

As a follow-up interaction, some of the funders agreed to participate in a short interview to provide more details about the situation in their countries, regarding the development of OA policy for books (see details in section 2.3.2).

2.3.1.2 Impact Survey

One of the activities of T5.2 was a survey conducted to learn more about stakeholder expectations regarding the PALOMERA project's outcomes by gathering their feedback on specific objectives. Participants were asked to formulate recommendations they would like to see included in the project. One RFO representative stated the following:

Identify common principles in open access book policies that funders developing new policies should mandate. Identify policies and strategies research organisations can adopt to support the transition to open access.

The respondents proposed several recommendations. Firstly, they suggested that quality assurance should be included for OA books funded by public money. They also emphasised the need to raise awareness of OA books. Additionally, they recommended providing mentoring and training to researchers on publishing models that do not require processing charges, as well as on open licensing and metadata. Importantly, they highlighted the necessity of addressing funding availability for OA books and increasing financial support for them.

2.3.1.3 Policy Life Cycle survey

Additionally, when considering a new open access book policy, a project plan should be created that encompasses all aspects of the life cycle - from initial research to policy launch and monitoring and evaluation. As a result, funders were asked to participate in another survey dedicated to the policy lifecycle, which ran from June 15th to August 15th. This policy life cycle was divided into six phases: 1) research, 2) policy formulation, 3) public consultation, 4) implementation, 5) monitoring and impact, and 6) evaluation and review.

Funders who have developed and implemented OA policies for books (or are in the process of doing so) were invited to share their experiences regarding each phase of the life cycle. Ten national research funders in the European Research Area provided their

responses, which were summarised in two articles¹⁹ published in the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit as a PALOMERA project output.

Funders explained that, while developing their policies, they mainly surveyed the existing policies of other funders or sought out existing recommendations regarding the contextual aspects of the document. Some reached out for advice from experts or research institutions. Policies were often written by individual staff members dedicated to open science tasks and policy development or by a group of staff members. Public consultations were conducted by a few funders; in other cases, researchers and research institutions were informed ahead of time before the policy came into effect. Policies were launched on funders' websites or announced earlier by top-level officials. Many RFOs monitor compliance using their own tools; some use a CRIS, while others rely on third-party services. Most funders currently lack tools for monitoring policy impact but plan to adopt steps in the future. Two funders pointed to services provided by OAPEN as impact monitoring tools. Four of the RFOs are preparing a review of policy evaluation. The feedback to this survey also gave input and inspiration for the policy development tool (section 3).

2.3.2 Interviews

Interviews with representatives of five RFOs were scheduled for February and March 2024 as a follow-up of the survey. They were asked additional questions regarding the current regulations of their agency in terms of providing funding, mandates, or recommendations on publishing OA books, and to elaborate further on the biggest challenges they encounter as funders.

The main challenge identified by funders in the survey was the financial situation of their country or funding agency. This was confirmed by the interviewees, who also identified other areas of concern:

- funding sustainability - since the budget is regulated by Ministry,
- legal constraints to set up a separate fund for open access publications,
- discoverability of open access books,
- standardised metadata,
- AI in text mining on big data - open access books in machine-readable format and Text and Data Mining licence,
- the role of the national library as a open access repository in the green route,
- incentives for researchers publishing open access books.

¹⁹ <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/open-access-book-policies/article/policy-life-cycle-for-oa-books> & <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/open-access-book-policies/best-practises-and-different-case-studies/article/processes-surrounding-open-access-book-policy-formulation-and-implementation>

As an alternative to the current funding situation, the interviewees proposed channelling funder financial support to promote various initiatives that are not-for-profit, such as new university presses/library based publishing and learned societies, or granular OA publishing aspects of each research step (research problem, method, analysis, peer review) on an open publishing platform, rather than publishing the final output in OA at a high cost.

Funder representatives were also engaged by the IBL-PAN research team of T2.2 through individual interviews conducted as a part of PALOMERA qualitative data collection activities in WP2. Out of 39 individual interviews, funders (RFOs) were engaged in 10 of the interviews. The interview scenario was structured around PESTLE factors. The full transcripts are included in the Knowledge Base²⁰, with some exceptions due to publishing restrictions. All interviews lasted around 60 minutes. The interviews were transcribed with HappyScribe, translated into English via DeepL (if required), proofread and anonymised (see footnote 11). For analysis purposes, interviews were pre-coded using PESTLE tags in the MAXQDA environment and subsequently analysed through in vivo coding (see footnote 18).

2.3.3 Developing recommendations for RFOs

As promised in the Grant Agreement, the main goal of the PALOMERA project was to develop evidence-based and actionable recommendations and support measures to align efficient policies and strategies for OA books, focusing on RFOs and RPOs, while also including the views of other stakeholders.

During the Funder Forum meetings, funder representatives shared the challenges they faced, but in many cases, they also discussed the solutions they have applied in their long journey of OA books policy development. Some challenges remain unresolved because they require collaborative work among all stakeholders engaged in the research life cycle, which is reflected in the proposed recommendations. As explained at the Funder Forum, due to the application of the Chatham House Rule, not all notes taken during meetings could be used (nothing that was said was attributed to who said it) as direct evidence to support the recommendations. However, all these voices were heard, collected, and reflected in the recommendations created as one of the project's final outcomes.²¹

²⁰ The Interviews' collection in the PALOMERA Knowledge Base:
<https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/collections/ef4a289b-2333-496d-82a8-ce701abe3f17>

²⁴<https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/results/recommendations-for-open-access-academic-book-policies/>

2.3.4 Validation exercises

RFOs have been important stakeholders of the project's validation process to manage the review of the Key Exploitable Results (Knowledge Base, data analysis and recommendations). Together with other stakeholders, RFOs participated in the first validation exercise (January 2024) focused on the Knowledge Base (KB) in order to (i) add more information to the KB to improve its representativity and completeness and to (ii) reflect upon the KB as a whole, preparing the ground for the analysis. It also asked participants to envision the potential usage of the KB in their specific context. Additionally, the RFOs participated in the third validation exercise (September 2024) where stakeholders were asked to identify necessary adaptations to be brought to the first drafts of the recommendations (using a validation by improvement strategy). A full report²² of the validation exercises process and results have been published in the PALOMERA Zenodo community.²³

²² Rabar, U., Mounier, P. (2024) PALOMERA D5.3 - Validation Report, <https://zenodo.org/records/10777636>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/palomera/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3 Service B: Policy Development Tool

3.1 Introduction

As the world of academic publishing continues to evolve, there is a growing need for clear and accessible policies that support open access while also balancing the diverse needs of stakeholders within the research and publishing ecosystems. The idea of the Policy Development Tool is to support policymakers in the formulation and implementation of policies and strategies for OA books. From the outset, partners were aware of existing tools²⁴ created elsewhere to help funders and other policymakers interested in generating an open access/open science policy tailored to their specific needs, offering them language/phrasing samples to be incorporated in the policy text or by helping them to create a checklist of items that their policy should consist of. Another existing tool, for example, provides opportunities to openly create a policy document in a collaborative way.

The concept of a Policy Development Tool was designed for policymakers at two levels: 1) For those who take strategic decisions about the overall direction of the policy but also 2) for those who actually write the policy. For the first group the tool would help raise awareness of the elements that should be addressed to make a robust and efficient OA book policy while also providing examples of how other policymakers have formulated similar policies. For the second group the tool would work as a checklist or a manual providing support in the formulation and implementation phase of the policy by using the PALOMERA Knowledge Base.

The conceptualisation of the tool came about in an internal project workshop that also took into consideration needs expressed by RFOs at several Funder Forum meetings. During the workshop it became clear that the tool should have navigational properties that can help policymakers set their own direction while paying attention to the perspectives of other stakeholders and other important landmarks identified in the research carried out in the PALOMERA project. These landmarks are referred to as key policy elements in the WP3 research and are the outcome of the research contained in the Knowledge Base²⁵. The tool has, therefore, been conceptually designed around those elements while taking into consideration the recommendations arising from WP4. In this way the tool also serves policy alignment helping policymakers adopt a multi-stakeholder perspective when developing policies. This should increase the

²⁴ For example <https://www.orfg.org/policy-development-guide> and <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/open-policy-making-toolkit/getting-started-with-open-policy-making>

²⁵ <https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/home>

chances of an efficient policy because the policy would anticipate the feasibility of implementation by the various stakeholders.

Figure 6

Visualisation of the OA Book Policy Compass

The idea of the Policy Development Tool is to pull in the evidence in the Knowledge Base, the research undertaken, and the recommendations. On this evidence base, the tool could provide policymakers with sound and comprehensive navigational support when developing OA book policies or strategies. We have therefore provisionally named the tool the *OA Book Policy Compass* (see Figure 6).

The OA Book Policy Compass (hereafter referred to as the ‘Compass’) is envisioned as a step-by-step guide for policymakers in developing policies related to open access books. The Compass is part of the PALOMERA project WP4, Task 4.2. By offering practical advice and a structured approach, the OA Book Policy Compass could help organisations navigate the complexities of policy formulation and implementation. The idea is to have a tool that is flexible enough to consider diverse policy contexts, whilst providing guidance on what elements are essential when creating a sound policy for OA books.

3.2 Compass design

The development of OA book policies should take into consideration the perspectives of a variety of stakeholders, such as RFOs, RPOs, national policymakers, libraries, publishers, researchers, scholarly societies, and infrastructure providers. The OA Book

Policy Compass is designed to consider these stakeholder perspectives (fostering alignment) while being tailored specifically for policymakers.

The aim of the OA Book Policy Compass is to serve as a versatile tool that can be adapted to a variety of contexts. Whether for those new to OA book policy or for organisations looking to refine existing policies, the Compass should prove valuable.

For organisations just starting their journey towards OA book policy development, the Compass will offer a straightforward, step-by-step guide to understand and consider key OA book policy concepts with examples of policy formulation and – potentially – ways of implementation. Moreover, it can help organisations align their policies with best practices in the field, ensuring that their approach is both forward-thinking and implementable. As such, the Compass will provide a framework for engaging with those other stakeholder groups mentioned above throughout the policy development process, encouraging a balanced approach to the various stakeholder perspectives.

The content of the Compass would include an introduction and a web-based and interactive table with navigational elements which would mainly consist of the key policy elements derived from the analysis findings (WP3) as described in Table 5 below.

Table 5 Key policy elements with short descriptions as input for the framework of the Compass.

Policy Element	Description
Policy Scope	
Scope: Types of Books	The scope of book-related content covered by the policy, including book chapters, monographs, edited volumes, and other types of scholarly publications.
Scope: Authors	Who the policy applies to, defining who is subject to its requirements regarding open access publication. Example: institution-wide, or department- or discipline-specific.
OA Models	
OA Models	Specific OA model(s) that the policy prescribes or encourages, such as Gold OA (OA through publisher, often involving a fee), Green OA (self-archiving in a repository), or Diamond OA (OA through publisher without any fees).
Rights and Licensing	
Licensing	The type of open licences recommended or required for OA publications under the policy. Example: CC BY, CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC-ND
Grant of Rights/Copyright Retention	Provisions to ensure that the author retains the rights to publish OA, such as recommending a non-exclusive publishing agreement.

Practical Implementation	
Time of Deposit	A designated timeframe within which authors are required to make their work OA under the policy.
Deposited Version	A specific version of the work that authors are required to deposit or make OA under the policy (e.g., pre-print, post-print, publisher's version).
Publishing Venue Restrictions	Limitations for the selection of publishing venues for compliance with the policy's requirements (e.g., national lists, DOAJ/DOAB)
Funding	
Funding Availability	Whether funding is provided for covering article (APC) or book processing (BPC) charges as part of the policy.

Compliance and Enforcement	
Exceptions	Specific circumstances or scenarios where certain rules or requirements might not apply, offering flexibility to authors and publishers.
Compliance Monitoring	Mechanisms by which adherence to the OA policy is assessed and verified, ensuring that authors and institutions fulfil the stipulated requirements.
Incentives for Compliance	Positive motivations or benefits offered to authors and institutions who adhere to the OA policy.
Disincentives for Non-Compliance	Consequences or penalties for authors or institutions who do not follow the OA requirements, discouraging non-compliance.
Policy Management and Alignment	
Policy Review Schedule	Regular intervals or timelines at which the OA policy undergoes evaluation, updating, or revision to ensure its relevance and effectiveness.
Policy Licence	Indicates whether the policy document itself is released under a specific licence that governs how the policy text can be used, shared, and modified.
Plan S	Is Plan S mentioned? The principles are to be implemented step by step by all universities and universities of applied sciences.

The funder would be prompted to consider and take decisions for each element and be supported by links to external resources, including the Knowledge Base (WP2), which holds information on OA academic book policies across the ERA. As an example feature

of the Compass, extracts from policies in the Knowledge Base could provide the policymaker with examples of how others have addressed and phrased the different elements.

To ensure that policies are both relevant and impactful, the OA Book Policy Compass would encourage users to carefully consider the broader national and international environments in which their organisations operate. This includes: a) identifying existing OA book policies, b) defining the scope of books and authors to be included, c) determining which elements of the local and global context should be taken into account, and d) drawing on existing good practices and policy documents to inform new policy development. For this purpose, the Knowledge Base (WP2) provides a rich and useful resource.

To further support policy implementation, the Compass would make use of the policy lifecycle (see Figure 7) developed as part of the PALOMERA project and described in the OAPEN OA Books article *Policy Life Cycle*.²⁶

Figure 7
Policy Life Cycle

Based on the best practices contained in the Knowledge Base, the research, and the Recommendations, policy templates can be designed for each phase of the Policy Life Cycle that contain the minimal set of elements that need to be included in a policy, and that then can be adapted to the local situation of the funder.

²⁶ <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/open-access-book-policies/policy-life-cycle>

4. Appendix 1 - Funder Forum meeting agendas

Funder Forum 1st meeting

Date: 23 May 2023

Time: 14h00 - 16h30 (CEST)

Place: Zoom

1. Welcome and introduction to the programme (5 min.)
2. [PALOMERA](#) project overview (10 min.)
3. Interactive session in smaller groups - moderated group discussions and knowledge exchange about open access book policy development and implementation (60 min.)

Coffee Break (10 min.)

4. Plenary session - feedback from the group discussions (50 min.)
5. Themes for future Funder Forum meetings (10 min.)
6. Next steps (5 min.)
7. Close of meeting.

The meeting will be held under the Chatham House Rule, which means that participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed. The meeting will not be recorded but notes will be taken. No personally identifiable information will be reported and responses to questions, discussion and comments will be summarised only. Should you wish to stop participating, this can be done at any time without any repercussion, however, due to the anonymised nature of any summary report, it may not be possible to identify and remove inputs after the point at which they are anonymised. The summarised and anonymised input of the group discussions will be shared with you and the other participants and used by the PALOMERA project to perform analyses relevant to the project. PALOMERA data privacy policy <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/privacy-policy-palomera>

Funder Forum 2nd meeting

Date: Monday 20 November 2023

Time: 15h00 - 17h30 (CET)

Place: Zoom

1. Welcome, tour de table, and introduction to the programme (10 min.)
2. Funder presentations focusing on implementation and monitoring (40 min.)
 - a. Austrian Science Fund
 - b. Norwegian Research Council
 - c. UKRI
 - d. FECYT
3. OAPEN presentation on infrastructures supporting funders (15 min.)

Coffee Break (10 min.)
4. Moderated group discussions inspired by the presentations (30 min.)
5. Plenary session - feedback from the group discussions (30 min.)
6. Next steps (10 min.)
7. Close of meeting.

The meeting will be held under the Chatham House Rule, which means that participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed. The meeting will not be recorded but notes will be taken. No personally identifiable information will be reported and responses to questions, discussion and comments will be summarised only. Should you wish to stop participating, this can be done at any time without any repercussion, however, due to the anonymised nature of any summary report, it may not be possible to identify and remove inputs after the point at which they are anonymised. The summarised and anonymised input of the group discussions will be shared with you and the other participants and used by the PALOMERA project to perform analyses relevant to the project. PALOMERA data privacy policy <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/privacy-policy-palomera>

Funder Forum 3rd meeting

Date: Tuesday 14 May 2024

Time: 14:00 - 16:00 (CEST)

Place: Zoom

1. Welcome and introduction to the programme (5 min.)
2. PALOMERA project update - where are we now? (5 min.)
3. Short presentation of the PALOMERA [Knowledge Base](#) (10 min.)
4. Knowledge exchange: Two presentations: Jean-Claude Kita from FNRS/Belgium and Mirjam Dular from ARIS/Slovenia, incl. questions (30 min.)
5. *Short break* (5 min.)
6. Open access book policy overview and PALOMERA survey results (20 min.)
7. Exploring hosting panel discussions around key policy themes (15 min.)
8. Introduction to the drafting of recommendations process for research funders (15 min.)
9. Next steps and the PALOMERA conference (28-29 Oct in Ljubljana, Slovenia) (10 min.)
10. Close of meeting (5 min.).

The meeting will be held under the Chatham House Rule, which means that participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed. The meeting will not be recorded but notes will be taken. No personally identifiable information will be reported and responses to questions, discussion and comments will be summarised only. Should you wish to stop participating, this can be done at any time without any repercussion, however, due to the anonymised nature of any summary report, it may not be possible to identify and remove inputs after the point at which they are anonymised. The summarised and anonymised input of the group discussions will be shared with you and the other participants and used by the PALOMERA project to perform analyses relevant to the project.

PALOMERA data privacy policy <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/privacy-policy-palomera>

Funder Forum 4th meeting

Date: Tuesday 29 October 2024

Time: 9:00 - 13:00 (CEST)

Place: In-person workshops, Location: [ZRC SAZU](#), Novi trg 2, Ljubljana, Slovenia

08:00-09:00 **Coffee and arrival**

09:00-11:00 **Workshop 1**

Workshop on the future of the Funder Forum (all funder representatives)

Summary of the workshop and next steps (Niels Stern)

11:00-11:30 **Coffee break**

11:30-13:00 **Workshop 2**

Workshop on the future of the Knowledge Base and the idea of a Policy Development Tool (all funder representatives)

Summary of the workshop and next steps (Niels Stern)

The meeting will be held under the Chatham House Rule, which means that participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed. The meeting will not be recorded but notes will be taken. No personally identifiable information will be reported and responses to questions, discussion and comments will be summarised only. Should you wish to stop participating, this can be done at any time without any repercussion, however, due to the anonymised nature of any summary report, it may not be possible to identify and remove inputs after the point at which they are anonymised. The summarised and anonymised input of the group discussions will be shared with you and the other participants and used by the PALOMERA project to perform analyses relevant to the project.

PALOMERA data privacy policy <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/privacy-policy-palomera>